

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART I. GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

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Bismuth phenylarsonate is practically insoluble in water. It has been shown that it can be quantitatively precipitated at a pH (5.1-5.33) from a solution containing acetic acid buffered with sodium or ammonium acetate. Methods for the estimation and separation of bismuth from salts of thallium (*ous*), alkalis, alkaline earths (*e.g.*, calcium strontium, barium, magnesium), copper, silver, lead, mercury, cadmium, cobalt, nickel, zirconium, thorium and tin as also in presence of sulphate ions have been described.

During the last few years a number of methods for the determination of bismuth has been described. These are, however, often complicated or involved the use of costly reagents. It is well known that the phosphate and arsenate of bismuth are sparingly soluble. Attention was directed to organic arsenical derivatives with the expectation that the precipitate would improve in quality and purity and might be of definite composition and suitable for direct weighing. These criteria were realised in the phenylarsonic acid compound. This acid is readily prepared in good yield by the method of Palmer and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1361).

Bismuth has been estimated by this reagent both gravimetrically and volumetrically with excellent results. In an acetic acid solution, buffered with sodium or ammonium acetate, it gave an insoluble basic salt of the composition $C_6H_6AsO_4Bi$ in which the percentage of bismuth was only 49.06. This compound of bismuth was found to be soluble in excess of dilute mineral acids or acetic acid and to decompose into hydroxide in presence of dilute alkali or ammonia.

Besides forming a basic compound with bismuth, it formed, with other common elements, compounds which were found to be more or less soluble in mineral acids or acetic acid.

Mercury (*ic* and *ous*), cadmium and lead ions gave white precipitates, and cupric, a greenish white with the reagent solution in water. With ferric ion, a cream coloured, with cobaltous, a red, and with aluminium, zinc, silver and manganese, white precipitates in presence of sodium acetate were obtained. The precipitates due to cobalt, silver, mercury (*ic*), cadmium, zinc and copper were soluble in potassium cyanide. The mercurous compound dissolved in potassium cyanide or ammonium acetate solution with the usual separation of metallic mercury. Mercury (*ic*) and lead compounds were further soluble in solutions of ammonium acetate. Thallous, alkali and alkaline earth salts gave no precipitate with the reagent even in presence of sodium or ammonium acetate.

Bismuth has been separated from silver, copper, cadmium, cobalt and nickel in presence of potassium cyanide and from mercury (*ic*) and lead in presence of ammonium acetate. Since the reagent precipitates quantitatively zirconium, thorium and tin in acid solutions and bismuth phenylarsonate remains in solution in presence of acids, bismuth has been easily estimated in the filtrates obtained after the separation of the said metals by the methods outlined below. Bismuth can also be estimated in presence of sulphate ions. The estimation may further, be conducted even in presence of salts of alkalis and of alkaline earths (Ca, Sr, Ba, Mg etc.), for they do not produce a precipitate with the reagent.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of the Reagent.—The reagent was prepared according to the method submitted by Bullard and Dickey ("Organic Synthesis", 1935, Vol. XV, p. 59). The light yellow crystals obtained were crystallised from water, using decolourising carbon, and recrystallised to free it from traces of chloride. The melting point of the crystal was $156-57^{\circ}$ with decomposition and the yield was about 47% of the theoretical.

Composition of the Bismuth salt of Phenylarsonic Acid.—Bismuth subnitrate (Kahlbaum) was dissolved in nitric acid and reprecipitated with water and dissolved in the least quantity of nitric acid (*pro analysi*). To this solution, diluted with a large volume of water, was added an excess of the reagent solution and a few grams of sodium acetate and boiled for some time with stirring till the precipitate became crystalline. The solution was filtered, washed with hot water till free from excess of the reagent and dried at 110° for an hour.

For the determination of composition, a weighed quantity of the sample so prepared, was slowly ignited in a porcelain crucible over Bunsen burner, dissolved in hydrochloric acid and diluted such that the solution was $0.3N$ in acid. The solution was saturated with hydrogen sulphide, heated to coagulate the precipitate, filtered and washed with a solution of sodium sulphide. The sulphide precipitate was then dissolved in nitric acid and the bismuth was determined as phosphate according to the method of Schoeller and Waterhouse (*Analyst*, 1920, **45**, 435) as the weighed sample contained less than 0.1 g. of bismuth (Schoeller and Lambie, *Analyst*, 1937, **62**, 533). (i) Wt. of sample = 0.0880 g.; Wt. of BiPO_4 = 0.0626 g. and therefore bismuth = 48.9%.

A tentative suggestion for the formula of the bismuth compound was $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{AsO}_3 \cdot \text{Bi}(\text{OH})$ which contains 49.06% of bismuth.

Reagents.—In the estimations, all reagent quality chemicals were used except where specifically mentioned. Reagents were: prepared and crystallised phenylarsonic acid (1g. in 100 c. c. water), a 10% solution of sodium acetate in water and a 10% solution of ammonium acetate in water and acetic acid about 2N.

Standard Solutions

Bismuth subnitrate was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid and made up to a definite volume with water. The bismuth content of the solution per c.c. was determined by taking a definite quantity of the solution in a weighed porcelain crucible, evaporating to dryness and igniting it to oxide (Miller and Van Dyke Cruser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 116). The bismuth content was further checked by estimating as phosphate (Schoeller and Waterhouse. *loc. cit.*)

Copper.—Electrolytic copper was dissolved in nitric acid and diluted with water to a definite volume. A measured quantity of the solution was fumed with concentrated H_2SO_4 and the copper content determined electrolytically.

Cadmium.—Kahlbaum's purest quality cadmium carbonate was dissolved in nitric acid and made up to a desired volume with water. From a definite amount of the solution cadmium was estimated as sulphate.

Mercury.—Mercurous nitrate was converted to mercuric nitrate by repeated evaporation with concentrated nitric acid and then diluted with water to a certain volume. The mercury content of the solution per c. c. was determined as sulphide by Volhard's method.

Silver.—Silver nitrate was dissolved in a definite amount of water whose silver content was determined as chloride from an aliquot part of the solution.

Cobalt.—Kahlbaum's 'nickel free' cobalt nitrate was dissolved in a certain volume of water. From a measured quantity of this solution cobalt was estimated as sulphate.

Nickel.—A solution was prepared with 'cobalt free' nickel nitrate of Kahlbaum and by the oxime method its amount of nickel was determined from a measured quantity of the solution.

Sulphate.—Hydrated sodium sulphate was ignited in a platinum basin to anhydrous salt. Weighed quantities of this anhydrous salt were used during the experiments.

Zirconium.—Kahlbaum's pure zirconium nitrate was treated with a few c. c. of conc. HCl and then diluted with water to a desired volume. From a measured amount of this solution, zirconium was determined by the methods of James, Fogg and Rice (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 895).

Thorium.—A thorium nitrate solution was prepared from Kahlbaum's pure quality sample and its amount of thorium determined, according to the method of James, Fogg and Rice (*loc. cit.*) from a measured quantity of the solution.

Tin.—A stannous chloride solution was prepared in water with a few c. c. of conc. HCl and its amount of tin, as oxide, was determined according to the methods of Knapper, Craig and Chandler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3945) from a definite amount of the solution.

Lead.—Standard solution of lead from lead acetate was prepared and its lead content, per c. c. was determined as sulphate.

Estimation of Bismuth

I. To a nitric acid solution of bismuth was added an excess of the reagent solution, diluted to 250 c. c., and a few c. c. of sodium acetate to neutralise the mineral acid. The mixture was boiled with stirring till the precipitate, which was at first gelatinous, became crystalline. If the precipitate was found to remain gelatinous, a little excess of sodium acetate should be added. A large excess of sodium acetate or prolonged boiling with excess of sodium acetate should be avoided, as these led to low results possibly due to the decomposition of the precipitate to oxide. The precipitate was then allowed to settle, filtered hot through Gooch crucible and washed with hot water. Six or seven washings after transferring on the Gooch was found to free the precipitate from the excess of sodium acetate or the reagent. This was then dried at 110-120° and weighed. The amount of bismuth was found by multiplying the weight of the bismuth compound with the factor 0.4906.

The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Sodium acetate.	Bi found.
1	0.04733 g.	15 c.c.	20 c.c.	0.04743 g.
2	0.0757	25	20	0.0760
3	0.02367	10	10	0.02374
4	0.09466	40	40	0.09517
5	0.1183	50	40	0.1181
6	0.04733	25	50	0.04720

TABLE II

No.	Bi taken.	Reagent added	Bi found
1	0.04733 g.	20 c.c.	0.04730 g.
2	0.0568	25	0.0568
3	0.09466	40	0.09504
4	0.03084	10	0.03081
5	0.1233	30	0.1233

II. An excess of the reagent solution was added to a solution of bismuth containing some free nitric acid. The solution was then neutralised with dilute ammonia (about 2N) using

Wesselow's indicator, and after acidifying it with dilute acetic acid a slight excess (2 c. c.) of this acid and ammonium acetate solution (20 c.c.) were added. A large excess of acetic acid solution or ammonium acetate should be avoided. The mixture was diluted to 250 c.c. and boiled with stirring till the precipitate became crystalline. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, washed and dried as mentioned above. The results appear in Table II.

Solubility in water.—To examine the solubility of the bismuth salt of phenylarsonic acid in water a weighed quantity of the bismuth precipitate in a gooch crucible dried at 110° - 120° was washed twice with 400 c.c. portions of hot water, again dried and weighed. Practically there was no loss in weight. The compound is insoluble in water.

The total washings were evaporated to a small volume and no precipitation or colouration was observed when this was saturated with hydrogen sulphide.

Determination of p_H .—For the determination of p_H bismuth was precipitated by both the procedures. The p_H of the first filtrates from both, was determined with quinhydrone electrode and found to be between 5.1 to 5.33.

TABLE III

Procedure I.				Procedure II.				
Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Sodium acetate.	Bi found.	p_H .	Bi taken	Reagent added.	Bi found.	p_H .
0.0252 g.	10 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.02516 g.	5.16	0.0252 g	10 c.c.	0.02521 g.	5.22
0.0252	10	10	0.02521	5.1	0.0252	10	0.02521	5.33

The Estimation of Bismuth in presence of Sulphate Ions.—An excess of the reagent solution was added to a solution of bismuth and sodium sulphate, containing sufficient nitric acid to keep the precipitated sulphate in solution. If any precipitate separated due to the addition of the reagent, that was dissolved by warming with a few c.c. of nitric acid. The solution was then cooled, neutralised with dilute ammonia (2N) using Wesselow's indicator, acidified with the dilute acetic acid, 2 c.c. excess of which were added. After the addition of 20 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution it was diluted to 250 c.c. and then the usual procedure followed. If the precipitate formed after the addition of the reagent was not dissolved by nitric acid but kept as such, it was found to be contaminated with the sulphate ions. Results appear in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	Bi taken.	Sodium sulphate taken.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	0.03084 g.	1 g.	10 c.c.	0.03081 g.
2	0.03084	3	10	0.03081
3	0.03084	6	10	0.03091
4	0.1790	5	50	0.1789

TABLE V

Cu and Bi taken.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
Cu.		
0.04733 g	20 c.c.	0.04724 g.
0.1035	10	0.02365
0.04733	20	0.04730
0.02367	10	0.02374

The bismuth precipitates (Table IV) after the weighings were dissolved in hot dilute hydrochloric acid and were diluted to large volumes. To these solutions were added normal barium chloride solutions (a few c.c.) but no turbidity or opalescence due to the precipitations of barium sulphate were observed. This showed that the precipitates of bismuth were completely free from sulphate ions.

Separation of Bismuth from Copper, Silver, Cadmium, Cobalt and Nickel.—To a nitric acid solution, containing bismuth and any of the mentioned cation, was added an excess of the reagent for the complete precipitation of bismuth. The solution was then neutralised with dilute ammonia and then an excess of potassium cyanide sufficient to keep the other cations in solution added. The solution was acidified with dilute acetic acid just to acidity (using Wesselow's

indicator) then 2 c.c. excess of this acid along with 10 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution added, diluted to 250 c.c. and the usual way followed. Results appear in Tables V—IX.

TABLE VI

No.	Ag and Bi taken. Bi.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	0.03084 g.	0.2122 15 c.c.	0.03091 g.
2	0.03084	0.05305 15	0.03086
3	0.06167	0.05305 20	0.06162

TABLE VII

No.	Cd and Bi taken. Bi.	Reagent added	Bi found.
1	0.03084 g	0.0553 10 c.c.	0.03086 g.
2	0.03084	0.3318 15	0.03081
3	0.03084	0.1659 15	0.03091

TABLE VIII

No.	Co and Bi taken. Bi.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	0.03084 g.	0.0516 10 c.c.	0.03081 g.
2	0.03084	0.2064 15	0.03076
3	0.02238	0.2064 10	0.02237

TABLE IX

No.	Ni and Bi taken. Bi.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	0.03084 g.	0.0603 10 c.c.	0.03086 g.
2	0.02238	0.2412 15	0.02227
3	0.02238	0.0603 15	0.02242

In the filtrates copper, silver, cadmium, cobalt and nickel might be estimated by decomposing the cyanide with mineral acid and then precipitating out the above elements as sulphides.

Separation of Bismuth from Zirconium and Tin

From a mixed solution of bismuth and zirconium or bismuth and tin, containing 5% by volume of hydrochloric acid, zirconium was precipitated by the reagent solution (1%) by the method of James, Fogg and Rice (*loc. cit.*), and tin by that of Knapper, Craig, and Chandlee (*loc. cit.*). The zirconium precipitate was washed with 1% hydrochloric acid and the tin with 4% solution of ammonium nitrate. The respective filtrates together with the respective washings were evaporated to dryness and fumed with the least quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid. The dried residues were then dissolved in water with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis. From these solutions bismuth was determined by the method followed for the estimation of it in presence of the sulphate ions. Results are given in Table X.

TABLE X

	Metals taken.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	Bismuth Zirconium	0.02238g. 0.05	20 c.c. 0.02237g.
2	Bismuth Zirconium	0.02238 0.05	20 0.02242
3	Bismuth Tin	0.02238 0.0532	15 0.02242
4	Bismuth Tin	0.04476 0.0532	20 0.04474

TABLE XI

	Metals taken.	Reagent added.	Bi found.
1	Bismuth Thorium	0.02238g. 0.0525	15 c.c. 0.02232g.
2	Bismuth Thorium	0.04476 0.0525	20 0.04464

Separation of Bismuth from Thorium

From a hot solution (400 c.c.) of bismuth and thorium nitrates containing 75 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 5 g. of ammonium acetate, thorium was first precipitated out, like zirconium and tin, by the methods of James, Fogg and Rice (*loc. cit.*), adding dropwise the prepared reagent solution (1%). The thorium precipitates were filtered off, washed and dissolved in 30 c.c. (1:1) hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated (*loc. cit.*), with the addition of a few c.c. more of the reagent solution, as the first precipitate was found to be contaminated with slight traces of bismuth. The precipitate was washed several times with water. The total filtrate was evaporated to dryness, fumed with the least quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid and the bismuth estimated according to the method given under 'The estimation of bismuth in presence of sulphate ions.' Results appear in Table XI.

In the presence of small quantities of bismuth, reprecipitation was not necessary. The filtrate on drying was directly used for the estimation of bismuth by dissolving in water with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid.

Separation of Bismuth from Mercury.—An excess of the reagent solution was added to a solution of bismuth and mercury containing some free nitric acid. This was diluted to 250 c.c. with water, 10 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution were added and boiled with stirring. If the precipitate was not crystalline a further quantity should be added till the precipitate became so. It was then filtered hot, washed and dried in the usual way. Results appear in Table XI.

TABLE XII

	Hg and Bi taken.		Reagent added.	Am. acetate.	Bi found.	Pb and Bi taken.		Reagent added.	Am. acetate.	Sodium acetate.	
	Bi.	Hg.				Bi.	Pb.			Bi found.	
1	0.0252g.	0.0503	10 c.c.	20 c.c.	0.0252g.	0.03084g.	0.1424	15 c.c.	50 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.03076g.
2	0.0252	0.1006	10	30	0.02526	0.03084	0.2848	15	60	10	0.03091
3	0.0252	0.2012	10	40	0.0252	0.03084	0.0712	15	40	5	0.03081

TABLE XIII

Separation of Bismuth from Lead

A solution of lead acetate was added to a solution of bismuth nitrate and a few c.c. of nitric acid also added to dissolve any precipitate formed. After the addition of some excess of the reagent solution it was neutralised with dilute (2N) ammonia and acidified with the dilute acetic acid (using Wesselow's indicator). Excess of this (2 c.c.) acid and 20 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution were then added, diluted to 250 c.c. and boiled with stirring. Some more of the ammonium acetate solution along with a little quantity of sodium acetate, which helped the crystallisation, were added till the precipitate was crystalline. The precipitate was then filtered, washed, dried and weighed as usual. Results are given in Table XIII.

Interfering Ions

Anions like citrate, tartrate, oxalate, etc., which form complexes with bismuth should be absent otherwise the reagent would not produce a precipitate of bismuth. Phosphates, arsenates, fluorides etc., that form sparingly soluble salts of bismuth should likewise be absent. The presence of chloride ions always gave very low results, and so the chlorides should be removed by repeated treatment with concentrated nitric acid or fuming with concentrated sulphuric acid. Since the reagent precipitates salts of iron, aluminium, beryllium, uranium and titanium in presence of sodium or ammonium acetate, all these salts should be removed. Chromium which under similar conditions contaminates the bismuth compound of the reagent should be separated. Due to the instability of the cyanide complexes of zinc and manganese the metals could not be separated from bismuth.

Antimony also should not be present, as to keep it in solution, excess of mineral acid was required. Mercury (*ous*) should be converted to mercury (*ic*) as in the presence of ammonium acetate, some metallic mercury was precipitated.

The volumetric estimation of bismuth by this reagent will shortly be published.

My best thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây for the facilities received in working out this piece of work in his laboratory.

N. B.—Out of a large number of agreeing results with varying proportions of the elements some are recorded in the paper. (Editor.)